

EMI TORQUE WN CONFIG

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EUROPEAN MIDDLEWARE INITIATIVE

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EMI TORQUE WN config

Functional Description

The TORQUE WN config is a metapackage that consists of

- the configuration module, yaim-torque-client
- dependencies on the TORQUE batch system (client side)

System Administrator Documentation:

The TORQUE WN config is needed only on the WN. Follow the instructions present in the Generic Installation & Configuration for EMI 1:

- TORQUE WN Installation&Configuration

-- DoinaCristinaAiftimiei - 09-May-2011

This topic: EMI > CREAMTorqueWNConfig

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